
A Comprehensive Case Study on Modern Recommender Systems

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Abstract

The amount of data present on the internet is enormous and so are the number of options available. “On the Internet, where the number of choices is overwhelming, there is need to filter, prioritize and efficiently deliver relevant information in order to alleviate the problem of information overload, which has created a potential problem to many Internet users [1]”. Although search engines are good at delivering the information, they fail at personalizing the data which is why there is a need for Recommender Systems(RSs). Recommendation systems can be broadly classified based on filtering methods used like content-based, collaborative or a hybrid model. The paper will briefly discuss the working of a recommendation system and how exactly the content is filtered. Personalizing content on a digital platform is not an easy task as there is a bare minimum time to recommend suitable content when the user opens the site. The methodology used in developing a recommendation engine is completely different for every digital platform, so it is not possible to generalize them. So, we will briefly discuss the case studies of some of the state-of-the-art recommendation engines such as Netflix, Amazon, YouTube and Facebook and compare them with their current model. The trends for developing a recommendation engine have largely evolved following the advancement of deep learning over the last few years. The systems today are so sophisticated that they could predict whether or not we would like the article, song or a particular item even better than ourselves. This paper will describe the details of the frameworks used for deploying deep learning in famous recommender systems and some underlying concerns of data discretion and privacy when tracking user’s data. This paper explores the past and present trends of progress of the recommendation systems to understand the current research areas, and to predict the scope of RSs in the near future.

1. Introduction

Recommender systems are the systems developed to help users find relevant items from the large unstructured data available on a system database. “Recommendation systems are software tools and techniques whose goal is to make useful and sensible recommendations to a collection of users for items or products that might interest them [2]”. The internet is a huge collection of data and as an end-user, we interact with only the first “n” items that match our description which creates the long-tail problem. Recommender systems aim at solving this problem by filtering out only the user relevant items from this large list to give the top “n” items based on ranking. “Recommender systems are information filtering systems that deal with the problem of information overload by filtering vital information fragment out of large amount of dynamically generated information according to user’s preferences, interest, or observed behavior about item [1]”.

The recommendation systems on the web are based on the information generated by the user, which could be in the form of explicit or implicit. While explicit information includes the data collected from the user directly, implicit information takes into account other things such as location, browser history, browsing patterns etc., for making the recommendations. This however raises many issues concerning user's privacy. The objective of this paper is to study the role of deep learning in recommender systems in the coming days and also address the underlying issues concerning the user's privacy when more and more data is collected for personalization.

2. Purpose and Statement of Need

Let's think about it right. For all we know, recommender systems are some behind the scenes algorithms that help us show the "product" we might like. But there's more to that. Recommendation systems are everywhere and the moment we are on the internet, they start their work, trying to give the most personalized experience at every stage possible. It could be a simple google search to a very complicated user rating prediction. Consider a movie with a large star cast such as The Avengers and a person who has no clue about the franchise, but has seen a film starring Robert Downey Jr. multiple times, which means he perhaps likes it. The present day's algorithms are versatile enough to show the thumbnail with RDJ's still to promote their content. See a cycle here? Let me help you. The person who got no knowledge was introduced to this franchise and not only did the machine get more data about the customer, it can also now feed him with more movies in that franchise to get more watch hours and in turn more data, and make the subscription last longer. From the customer's perspective, he now has a whole new world of options to choose from, for his next ride. This is a win-win situation.

The critical point here is at promoting the content based on an "if". What if the user doesn't like the picture? Easy! Next time while recommending another movie from the franchise, the recommender system shows the thumbnail with multiple cast members excluding RDJ. If the user watches it, he is into the content, and if not then perhaps show him different suggestions. I wrote this particular example because the person here is me, and how I got to know about the famous franchise. This happened way back in the year 2014, and the progress recommender systems have made since then is exponential. I have been studying the trends in recommender systems for quite a while now, and this is a very interesting domain, which is sure to make much more progress in the near future. But a problem that is not well addressed is regarding the privacy concerns with the recommender system in the current day. These systems typically use a lot of user generated information that could be sensitive and might disrupt a user's right to privacy. Through this research I intend to study how different are the recommender systems used by many industries and what kind of data they use to generate suggestions. I also intend to study and analyze the scope of deep learning in the field of recommendation systems in the near future.

3. Literature Review

Recommender systems is a widely studied and researched subject in the tech industry. Recommender systems are the models that cannot be used in a unified approach because the user's behaviors and patterns change in time and it is important to analyze them on a very ground level. This is where deep learning outshines every other approach. Deep learning has been in the background since the 1970's, but once the speed of GPUs has grown significantly since the early 2000's, they are coming into practice in almost every industry.

S. Zhang et al. in his research [3] studied various deep learning based approaches that could very well influence the current day recommendation systems and also explained some problems and possible future extensions when using this approach in near future. M. Fu et al. also did tons of research in the field of

deep learning and studied the various architectures on two large datasets by Movielens as benchmarks. They confirmed that neural network based approaches outperforms many current state-of-the-art approaches by a margin [4]. B. Zhang et al. addressed various issues concerning user's privacy with extensive data collected from the user in the name of improving personalization and came up with a technique of implementing a control mechanism to allow for each user to choose what kind of information they share [5]. There are many other articles and papers cited below, which talk much in detail about some of the questions this research intends to answer.

4. Description

The goal of any recommendation engine is to recommend product(s) based on the user's previous interactions. What if the recommendation system doesn't have any information about the user's history. This creates the very well known cold-start problem. It could be solved by many approaches such as asking users about their preferences or suggesting them with different kinds of products to understand which one they like better. To solve this without requiring any explicit feedback, researchers are trying our deep learning to make personalization better. My first research question would be to understand "How does deep learning solve the cold-start problem and how does it help better analyze the user behavior?" Also, tons of research has been done about what kinds of data is collected by the various recommendation systems on the web but it is unclear how certain data is used for generating recommendations. Through this research, I intend to learn about "What kinds of behavioral data used by those systems for generating the recommendations and also how it could potentially violate the user's right to privacy?" To address these issues, it is important to understand the mechanism behind the working of the recommender systems.

5. How do these Systems work?

In order to learn about how a recommendation system triggers users' right to privacy, it is crucial to know their underlying principle. Recommender systems collect the data previously generated by the users, and use it to predict what the user may like. Amazon uses recommender systems to predict items, Netflix to suggest movies, Youtube to suggest videos, Facebook to suggest posts, and many more industries use recommendation systems. Recommender systems are powerful tools because they can predict user ratings for an item before the user actually rated that item, using their previous ratings for similar items [6]. The entire process of recommendation happens primarily in 3 phases:

1. **Information Collection Phase:** This phase involves taking feedback from the users which can be in the form of data, which can be implicit, explicit or both. "This information includes cognitive skills, intellectual abilities, learning styles, interest, preferences and interaction with the system [1]".
2. **The Learning Phase:** The data collected from the previous phase would be large and unstructured. This phase deals with filtering out relevant data and processing it to obtain significant insights.
3. **The Recommendation Phase:** After knowing about the user's behavior from the learning phase, the model recommends the products the user might prefer or like [1].

6. Filtering Techniques

6.1. Content based filtering:

"The main idea of content-based methods is to try to build a model, based on the available "features", that explain the observed user-item interactions [7]". Content based filtering needs to have the details about the item before actually labeling it. It works by grouping together products having similarities and based on the assumption that users like products with similar characteristics and recommends them to the user. This is not a very good method for recommendation since it involves a lot of hand-coding by adding labels for

each item. So, it is quite common to use content based filtering with other kinds of filtering techniques to improve the accuracy of the model.

6.2. Collaborative Filtering:

“The main idea that governs the collaborative methods is that through past user-item interactions when processed through the system [7]”. Collaborative filtering builds a database to match users and their item preferences. Collaborative filtering works by grouping together users having similar interests and based on the assumption that similar users like similar products, recommending products that are liked by one user to another user having similar likings. However, the major problem with collaborative filtering is the cold-start problem, when there is very little to no information available on the user.

6.3. Hybrid Filtering

Hybrid filtering is the most famous technique used in recommendations which is a combination of content based and collaborative filtering techniques to give much better recommendations. “Combining collaborative and content-based filtering together may help in overcoming the shortcoming we are facing at using them separately and also can be more effective in some cases [8]”. This is the most used technique in many of the modern day digital platforms.

7. Technical Aspects

The key element of any recommendation engine is data. Data is collected in many ways from the user and is used to compute a similarity index for recommending the products based on ranks. This data could be demographical or behavioral and can be explicit or implicit. The similarity index is calculated in many ways and through many filtering techniques mentioned in the paper. These filtering techniques can be probably replaced through deep learning to map the similarity index between user and the product. Deep learning models are trained through neural networks which can be of many types and have many applications. The way deep learning models are trained and deployed differs from each industry and for each different application. For example, Spotify uses ANNOY model for audio classification while facebook uses DeepText for text classification. Deep learning models convert data into high dimensional vectors through embeddings, and the embeddings used will be different for each use case. For example, classifying text would require less processing power so LSTMs are fine, but for larger training use cases such as for images or audio, require deep layers such as ResNet-50. Since recommendation systems are generally trained on large data, these BigData models cannot usually run on systems with smaller processing powers. Many of the modern day tech giants that run recommendation engines do it on multiple systems with very large GPU's for processing multiple computations simultaneously. NVIDIA's GPUs are the most popularly used ones capable of performing computations in multiple dimensions.

8. Case Studies on some renowned Recommender Systems

Before studying how deep learning could influence all kinds of recommendation systems in the near future, it is important to analyze the progress recommendation systems have made in the last 2 decades. This is done by studying some best of the class recommender systems operating in the backend today, and what makes them unique.

8.1. Amazon's Recommendation System

Amazon has about 20 million different products to show to 100 million users across the globe. Amazon gives us personalized recommendations based on your previous search history, previous purchases, current seasons running and see why those items were recommended. Amazon uses a recommender system to target high traffic websites and site the recommendations. Their recommender system primarily uses item-to-item collaborative filtering to target specific users for specific items. To match the item having the most similarity,

the amazon search creates tables having similar items and ranks them for each user based on the previous data available on them. To do this amazon has to analyze huge amounts of data to give a “personalized shop” experience to all the users who use their service. Amazon’s recommendation engine considers two kinds of information to do this: The information about the user and the product; and the dependencies and relations between them.

The first part in the information collection is simple, but usually suffers from a cold start problem. This is usually addressed by suggesting random products to the user during their first few minutes on the site, to analyze their browsing behaviors and patterns. But since the service already has a massive user database, they match the browsing patterns of the new user with others who searched for a similar product. And very much in the first few minutes itself, you get your personalized amazon store. Ofcourse, the more information present about the user, the better will be the personalization. ResNet-50 is the widely used architecture by Amazon for recommending products based on images. Amazon’s recommender system is well known to offer recommendations that might interest the user, they might not even think about.

8.2. YouTube’s Recommender system

YouTube has about 800 million videos which are viewed by 2.6 billion active users every day and is the second most viewed website in the world right after Google Search. In terms of data produced, there’s about 80 billion bytes of data that is produced every day. That data could be in terms of number of clicks, time watched, watch preferences and many other criteria. For such a large database, the recommendation video retrieval happens in two phases as demonstrated by Covington et al. in their paper. In this approach they explained the algorithm behind the scenes where one network generates the recommendations and the other network ranks them [9]. This is an intelligent approach that involves filtering the number of videos from millions into less than thousand before eventually ranking them in order to recommend to the user. A few years earlier, the YouTube’s recommendations seemed to be over-personalized, feeding them with same or similar videos over and over. Developer’s call YouTube’s algorithm the “Recipe Book” with more content added every second. YouTube is one of the first platforms to consider improving a user’s feed and to even recommend channels that are not very popular. YouTube is also working on improving their algorithm by also taking the user’s behavior through deep learning.

8.3. Netflix’s Recommender System

Netflix has about 6000 popular movies and TV shows and roughly 200 million subscribers. Unlike YouTube, Netflix is a paid platform and thus the recommendations should be on point to keep up the subscriber count. Netflix’s recommendation system works by estimating the likelihood a user watches a particular video. Since their product database is not as huge as that of YouTube, they assign scores to each movie for the chance of a particular user watching it and recommend the movies/shows by sorting them accordingly in each category. These scores are assigned to each video based on the User’s interactions with the service, the information they have about a particular title such as the genre, actor(s) present, duration etc., and what users with similar interests have watched. More than 80% of the time spent by the user of Netflix comes through the video recommendations on their homepage. Netflix’s recommendation system is so complex that it even takes into account the current device streaming on and the time of the day while recommending a video. For example, the recommendations shown on a television in the evenings would be different from the recommendations in the morning on a mobile for the same user. It is one of the companies making most out of their recommendation engine and is also the first to come up with the idea of different thumbnails to different users for the same show.

8.4. Spotify’s Recommender System

Similar to all other digital platforms, the current recommendation system used by Spotify works on content based as well as collaborative filtering. Spotify’s algorithm is based on a system called BaRT, which has two modes: exploration and exploitation [10]. The exploitation recommends songs based on the collaborative filtering use which happens when there is enough information available on the user. But when there is not enough information about the system or the user, the system fails to uncover if it has to recommend or uphold that recommendation to that user. This is when the exploration comes into picture where the algorithm recommends some random songs to gather more information about the user. “Exploration recommends content with uncertain predicted user engagement for the purpose of gathering more information. The importance of exploration has been recognized in recent years, particularly in settings with new users, new items, non-stationary preferences, and attributes [10]”. A song is considered a positive recommendation when a user listens to it for more than 30 seconds, and if not it is a bad one [10]. Spotify recommends these songs based on 12 different algorithms running together. Their most famous one thus far is ANNOY, which is an approximate nearest neighbor classification algorithm. This is different from the KNN as it compromises a bit of accuracy for much faster model training.

8.5. Facebook’s Recommender System

Facebook is a much more complicated case as it involves various features that are similar to other video recommendations, but they also have recommendations for groups, people we might know and also certain pages we might consider following. Facebook also has ads that are personalized according to the user, so there are a lot of things running in the background while we casually scroll through the feed. “Facebook uses Collaborative Filtering to recommend people you might know, display ads based on your posts, jobs you might like, groups you might want to follow, or companies you might be interested in [11]”. “Facebook also uses Apache Giraph to analyze the social graph formed by users and their connections. Apache Giraph is an iterative graph processing system built for high scalability [11]”. This might sound simple but consider the size of an average dataset for Facebook, which has about 500 billion ratings and more than 3 billion users, which is the largest graph network for any digital platform. It is impossible to design an algorithm to scale up with such massive data and hence Facebook came up with using neural networks to improve the model efficiency and performance and to recommend people with content most similar to them.

Keeping all the mentioned digital platforms in mind, and also considering others such as LinkedIn, Tinder or Pinterest, it is obvious that different applications need different kinds of recommendation systems and every use case differs. With billions of web users, these traditional approaches fail to address or read through every interaction they have with the user. But it is also very important to properly analyze user behavior in order to properly address each customer and to properly personalize the user’s feed during their interaction. This is where deep learning came into picture.

9. Deep Learning for Recommender Systems

Many tech companies are already using deep learning through different kinds of neural networks for improving customer experience. “For instance, YouTube, eBay, Yahoo, and Twitter choose deep neural networks (DNNs), while Spotify prefers convolutional neural networks (CNNs) [12]”. “The principal feature that differs DL-based recommender systems from traditional ones is coping with complex interaction patterns and precisely reflecting the user’s preferences [12]”. CNNs are extremely effective at processing unstructured data when feature extraction is done properly which makes them very useful for processing video, image, text or even audio. Also, CNNs help eliminate the cold start problem while also helping with the Collaborative filtering techniques used by traditional systems. RNNs are primarily used for session based recommendations based on the user’s click history in the current session. YouTube uses such a system to

recommend the next video based on the current video. This is because “The majority of websites today do not require a user to log in for navigation. In other words, it means no access to customers’ long-term interests or consumption habits [12]”.

10. Privacy Issues surrounding Recommender Systems

The way the recommendation system works is by collecting large amounts of data from the user. This causes many issues concerning the privacy of the user. Every second a user spends on the web, footprints are made on the web, which are continuously analyzed in many ways to personalize ads to ultimately generate more revenue. “Researchers, system developers, and policy makers have been creating solutions at all levels to cope with rising privacy concerns in online recommender systems and minimize the compromise of prediction accuracy [5]”.

Recommendation systems collect all kinds of behavioral data from the users which could be public such as product reviews or purchase history. They also collect sensitive information such as age, income, location, education, preferences etc. Although it is generally the user who grants the system permission to use this data, they are unaware of what exactly is the information the platforms collect. The research conducted by Bo Zhang et. al [5] confirmed that “There also is an asymmetric information problem between the service provider and the user—a lack of awareness could be another cause of the current finding [5]”. They also proposed a control mechanism to limit the amount of sensitive information a user shares on the web, but for this to effectively work they should be aware of the kind of data they chose to share. “Therefore, system designers should carefully weigh the advantages and disadvantages of a control mechanism in addressing privacy concerns depending on the data input type, data sensitivity levels, and the existence of an awareness mechanism [5].”

11. Discussion

Deep learning can analyze small parts of information to generate spot on recommendations and also require massive amounts of user data to train on. With the amount of data produced in the current era, deep learning is really the thing for recommendation systems. It could address various issues of cold start and can learn from even smaller behavioral data much effectively. Deep learning models can effectively process non-linear data which makes them more effective than the traditional ones. “Non-linear transformation, representation learning, sequence modeling, and flexibility are the principal benefits of applying DL for recommendations [12]”. That much amount of information about the user that is used to train the model raises privacy issues that are not properly addressed. So, it is critical to have a control mechanism that can be used by the user to share the amount of information they share, “so users are more confident about trading in their privacy for personalized services [5]”. This heightened awareness about selecting their preferences regarding what kind of information a user is ready to share, leads to lesser privacy concerns to make their time on the web more effective.

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